

THE MISSION SENSOR MICROWAVE IMAGER, ITS APPLICATIONS AND VALIDATION

Robert C. Lo and James P. Hollinger

Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, D.C.

Abstract

The Mission Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) is a multi-frequency microwave radiometric system designed to provide retrievals of the environmental parameters including sea ice morphology, sea surface wind, precipitation, atmospheric moisture content and soil moisture. It is a joint Navy/Air Force project developed by the Hughes Aircraft Company (HAC) under the direction of the Navy Space Systems Activity (NSSA) and the Air Force Space Division to be flown on the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP). The SSM/I is also included in the ensemble of instruments for the Navy-Remote Ocean Sensing System (N-ROSS). The Space Sensing Applications Branch of the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has served as a technical consultant to NSSA beginning in 1982. NRL has also drawn up a test and evaluation plan to quantify and evaluate the performance of the instrument and its processing algorithms.

1. Introduction

The microwave environmental sensor system, referred to as the SSM/I, is a joint Navy/Air Force Project (1). It is a passive microwave radiometric system developed by the Hughes Aircraft Company under the direction of the Navy Space Systems Activity (NSSA) and the Air Force Space Division to be flown on the DMSP operational spacecraft as an all weather oceanographic and meteorological sensor. The Space Sensing Applications Branch of NRL has served as a technical consultant to NSSA beginning in fiscal year 1982.

This presentation is intended to describe the SSM/I instrument, the geophysical retrieval algorithm, and the validation plan so that it might serve as an introduction to the SSM/I for those individuals who have an interest in the instrument or its geophysical data products.

2. Description of the SSM/I

The SSM/I is a seven-channel, four-frequency, linearly polarized passive microwave radiometric system. The instrument measures atmospheric/earth surface brightness temperatures at 19.35, 22.235, 37.0, and 85.5 GHz. These data will be processed by the Naval Oceanography Command to obtain near real time global precipitation maps, sea ice morphology, marine surface wind speed, columnar

integrated water vapor and liquid water, and soil moisture percentage. In addition, Navy and Air Force DMSP tactical sites will be capable of receiving these same data directly from the satellite to satisfy their unique customer mission requirements.

The DMSP Block 5D-2 satellite and the SSM/I are depicted in Figure 1. The instrument consists

Figure 1. The DMSP Block 5D-2 Satellite.

of an offset parabolic reflector of dimensions 24 x 26 inches, fed by a corrugated, broad-band, seven-port horn antenna. The reflector and feed are mounted on a drum which contains the radiometers, digital data subsystem, mechanical scanning subsystem, and power subsystem. The reflector-feed-drum assembly is rotated about the axis of the drum by a coaxially mounted bearing and power transfer assembly (BAPTA). All data, commands, timing and telemetry signals, and power pass through the BAPTA on slip ring connectors to the rotating assembly.

A small mirror and a hot reference absorber are mounted on the BAPTA and do not rotate with the

drum assembly. They are positioned off axis such that they pass between the feed horn and the parabolic reflector, occulting the feed once each scan. The mirror reflects cold sky radiation into the feed thus serving, along with the hot reference absorber, as calibration references for the SSM/I. This scheme provides an overall absolute calibration which includes the feed horn. Corrections for spillover and antenna pattern effects from the parabolic reflector are incorporated in the data processing algorithms.

The prototype of the SSM/I is shown in the stowed position in Figure 2 and deployed in Figure 3. The radiometers are total power, balanced mixer, superheterodyne type receivers. The exact operating frequencies and radiometric performance characteristics are given in Figure 4. The weight, size, power, and orbit specifications are given in Figure 5.

Figure 2. The prototype of the SSM/I in the stowed position.

Details of the scan geometry are shown in Figure 6. The SSM/I rotates at a uniform rate making one revolution in 1.9 seconds during which time the satellite advances 12.5 km. The antenna beams are at an angle of 45° to the BAPTA rotational axis, which is normal to the earth's surface. Thus as the antenna rotates the beams define the surface of a cone and, from the orbital altitude of 833 km, make an angle of incidence of 53.1° at the earth's surface. The scene is viewed over a scan angle of 102.4° centered on the ground track aft of the satellite resulting in a scene swath width of 1394 km. The radiometer outputs are sampled differently on alternate scans. During the scene portion of the scans labeled scan A in Figure 6, the five lower frequency channels are each sampled over 64 equal 1.6° intervals and the two 85.5 GHz channels are each sampled over 128 equal 0.8°

Figure 3. The prototype of the SSM/I in the deployed position.

SSM/I PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS

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PARAMETER	RADIOMETRIC PERFORMANCE			
	19.35 ± 0.05 VERT AND HORIZ	22.235 ± 0.05 VERT	37.0 ± 0.1 VERT AND HORIZ	85.5 ± 0.3 VERT AND HORIZ
IF BANDPASS, MHZ	10 TO 250	10 TO 250	100 TO 1000	100 TO 1500
RADIOMETRIC ACCURACY, K	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
ΔT, K	0.8	0.8	0.6	1.1
DYNAMIC TEMP RANGE, K	375	375	375	375
EFFECTIVE FOV (3 dB ANTENNA BEAMWIDTH, INCLUDES INTEG TIME) REFERENCE, KM	70 x 45	60 x 40	38 x 30	16 x 14
INTEGRATION TIME, mS	7.95	7.95	7.95	3.89

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Figure 4. SSM/I performance characteristics.

SSM/I RADIOMETER	
WEIGHT	107 LB
SIZE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANTENNA 24 x 26 IN. • ORUM 14 IN. DIAMETER 16 IN. HEIGHT
POWER	45 W
ORBIT	833 KM CIRCULAR 101 MINUTE PERIOD 98.7° INCLINATION - SUN SYNCHRONOUS
SWATH	1390 KM
SPACECRAFT	DMSP BLOCK 5D-2

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Figure 5. SSM/I radiometer specifications.

SCAN A
SCENE STATION/SCAN 128
FILE/SCAN 176
SCAN B
SCENE STATION/SCAN 128
FILE/SCAN 256
SCENE STATION/ORBIT 404 224
FILE/SECRET 1 313 728

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SSM/I SCAN GEOMETRY

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SSM/I ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS

PARAMETER	DESIRED GEOMETRIC RESOLUTION, KM	RANGE OF VALUES	QUANTIZATION LEVELS	ABSOLUTE ACCURACY
OCEAN SURFACE WIND SPEED	25	3 TO 25	1	± 2 M/S
ICE				
• AREA COVERED	25	0 TO 100	5	± 1%
• AGE	50	1ST YEAR, MULTYEAR	1 YR. > 2 YR.	NONE
• EDGE LOCATION	25	NA	NA	± 12.5 KM
PRECIPITATION OVER LAND AREAS	25	0 TO 25	0, 5, 10, 15, 20, > 25	± 5 MM/HR
CLOUD WATER**	25	0 TO 1	0.05	± 0.1 KG/M ²
LIQUID WATER***	25	0 TO 6	0.10	± 2.0 KG/M ²
PRECIPITATION OVER WATER	25	0 TO 25	0, 5, 10, 15, 20, > 25	± 5 MM/HR
SOIL MOISTURE	50	DRY - SATURATED	DRY - MOIST WET - SATURATED	NONE

* GOALS FOR SYSTEM
** < 100 μm DIAMETER
*** > 100 μm DIAMETER

Figure 7. SSM/I environmental parameters.

Figure 6. SSM/I scan geometry.

intervals or approximately each 11 km along the scan. During the alternate type B scans, only the two 85.5 GHz channels are sampled at 128 equal intervals. Sampling, to 12-bit precision, is accomplished by the integrate, hold, and dump method with an integration period of 7.95 milliseconds for the five lower frequency channels and an integration period of 3.89 milliseconds for the 85.5 GHz channels. Alternate 0.8° intervals are centered on the mid points of the 1.6° intervals so that samples of all seven channels are collected with additional 85.5 GHz samples equally space between them. Thus the five lower channels are sampled on an approximately 25 km grid along the scan and along the track. The two 85.5 GHz channels are sampled at one-half this spacing both cross and along track.

The hot absorber and cold sky reflector references are each sampled in the same manner as the scene data but over total angles of 8.0° as they occult the feed horn during the remaining portion of the scan.

The radiometer outputs are converted to absolute antenna temperature using the hot and cold sky reference measurements, and then corrected for antenna pattern effects to obtain absolute brightness temperatures. The brightness temperatures are then fed through a retrieval algorithm to estimate various environmental parameters. The measured environmental parameters, the geometric resolution, and the range, quantization, and absolute accuracy of the measurements are given in Figure 7.

3. The SSM/I Processing Algorithm

The SSM/I data processing algorithm in place at the Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center (FNO) and the Air Force Global Weather Center (AFGWC) was developed at Environmental Research and Technology, Inc. (ERT) (2) under a sub-contract from HAC. It is composed of four modules. The first of these, SMISDP, is called the sensor data processing module. It ingests and processes raw satellite data to produce earth-located brightness temperatures.

The major processing within this module include calibration, earth location, and antenna pattern correction.

The second module (SMIEPE) performs the extraction of environmental parameters based on the so-called D-matrix approach, except for ice parameters. The "D" matrix is composed of linear regression coefficients defining the relationship between observed brightness temperatures and environmental parameters. The coefficients are derived through geophysical models and climatological data. The formalism for the approach starts with the assumption that there exists some linear combination of brightness temperatures which will provide information about the geophysical parameters in question.

$$\underline{P} = \underline{D} \underline{I}$$

where \underline{P} is the vector of parameters, and \underline{I} is the vector of brightness temperatures and \underline{D} is the D-matrix. It can be shown that

$$\underline{D} = \underline{C}(\underline{P}, \underline{I}) \underline{C}^{-1}(\underline{I}, \underline{I})$$

where $\underline{C}(\underline{P}, \underline{I})$ is the correlation matrix between \underline{P} and \underline{I} and $\underline{C}^{-1}(\underline{I}, \underline{I})$ is the inverse of the auto-correlation matrix of \underline{I} . To derive the D-matrix, parameter values are calculated from radiosondes and climatology data. The brightness temperatures corresponding to the parameter values are calculated through geophysical models (1,2,3,4). This process is demonstrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. SSM/I algorithm development.

The assumption of linearity between \underline{P} and \underline{T} is not satisfied over the entire earth. Instead of adding higher order terms in the regression equations, a number of climate zones have been selected for the environmental parameter extraction algorithm. The climate zones are defined in Table 1. A D-matrix is developed for each of the climate zones. The D-matrices of the transition zones are averages of those of neighboring zones. Due to limitation of computing facility at AFGWC, the maximum number of channels used for the retrieval of each parameter is limited to four. The channel selections for all the parameters are shown in Table 2.

	DEGREES LATITUDE	SEASONS	BACKGROUNDS
TROPICAL	0° - 20°	WARM (JUN - NOV) COOL (DEC - MAY)	LAND, OCEAN
TRANSITION	20° - 25°	MULTISTEP AVERAGING BETWEEN TROPICAL AND MIDLAT	
MIDLAT	25° - 50°*	SPRING/FALL SUMMER (JUN - AUG) WINTER (NOV - FEB)	LAND, OCEAN
TRANSITION	SIMILAR TO PROCEDURE BETWEEN TROPICS AND MIDLAT		
ARCTIC	60°* - 90°	COOL (MAY - OCT) COLD (NOV - APR)	LAND, OCEAN (INCLUDING SEA ICE)

*EXCEPT FOR POSSIBLE SEA ICE AREAS, BOUNDARIES ARE DEFINED ACCORDING TO ICE DYNAMICS

Table 1

PARAMETERS	FREQUENCIES (GHz)			
	19	22	37	85
SW SURFACE WIND SPEED, OCEAN		X	X	X
RC PRECIPITATION OVER OCEAN		X	X	X
CWO CLOUD WATER		X	X	X
CWL CLOUD WATER		X	X	X
LWO LIQUID WATER		X	X	X
LWL LIQUID WATER		X	X	X
SM SOIL MOISTURE, LAND	X	X		
RL PRECIPITATION OVER LAND			X	X
IC CONCENTRATION			X	X
IA AGE			X	
IE EDGE LOCATION			X	

Table 2

The algorithm for ice concentration, IC, uses only the two 37 GHz channels (3,5)

$$IC = A_0 + A_1 [T_{BV}(37) - T_{BH}(37)]$$

where A_0 and A_1 are coefficients calculated from climatology values of ice temperatures, ice emissivities and atmospheric conditions. Ice temperature, T_I , is estimated through the following expression

$$T_I = [C_0 + C_1 \cdot T_{BV}(37)] / IC + C_2$$

If T_I is greater than the climatological values for multi-year ice, the ice is designated as first year ice. Otherwise it is designated as multi-year ice.

The third module, SMIVER, verifies the retrieved parameters against pre-selected climatology and surface truth field (5). The last module, SMIUPD, updates the coefficients used in the parameter extraction algorithms when the verification results meet certain pre-determined criteria (5).

4. The Test and Evaluation Plan

The main purpose for the NRL proposed Test and Evaluation (T/E) plan is to quantify and to assure the performance of the SSM/I instrument. In order to achieve these goals, both the space segment and the ground segment must be tested.

The SSM/I is a state-of-the-art passive microwave radiometer. It has been designed to avoid a good number of problems encountered in earlier instruments, particularly, the Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) which were flown on SEASAT and NIMBUS-7 satellites. Nevertheless, efforts must be made to avoid having unseen problems by neglecting an end-to-end radiometric test of the system (6), as was the case with SMMR. NRL proposed a scheme to calibrate the instrument before launch at a high altitude with relatively dry atmospheric conditions, and low RF interference such as on a mountain top. A number of different known targets of various sizes can be used for the calibration purpose. The performance of the system starting from feed horn down is measured as a whole. The NRL proposed scheme is able to measure the co- and cross-polarization beam efficiencies to 1-2 percent accuracy (6). The end-to-end calibration scheme resembles the performance of the instrument in space and enables discovery of unforeseen problems.

During the 90 days after launch, NRL plans to conduct T/E of the radiometric performance by making a number of underflights using the NRL SSM/I Simulator. Surface truth data will also be collected. The Simulator is an ensemble of radiometers which are at the same frequencies as the SSM/I. It will be flown on the Navy RP-3 aircraft and can be tilted at the same look angle as the spaceborne instrument. The Simulator antenna temperatures (T_A 's) can be compared to the corresponding SSM/I T_A 's for the test and evaluation of the space segment.

NRL has already collected benchmark data sets with the SSM/I Simulator for the purpose of validating the SSM/I processing software in place at FNOC. Such T/E effort has already started. Majority of the ground segment T/E must, however, be done post-launch. Environmental retrievals must be compared to carefully collected, high quality surface truth data. NRL's approach to the post-launch T/E effort includes identifying a Sensor Specialist for each environmental parameter. The Sensor Specialist then organizes a team of experts which will define the T/E model, cost out effort, define data platforms, schedule and coordinate

experiments, collect and analyze data, and report results. NRL will oversee and manage the overall T/E effort and will coordinate and assist each team all through the experiments. Presently, NRL has finished the overall Plan and identified Sensor Specialists for all ocean and ice parameters and started the post-launch T/E Plan for ice parameters. It awaits funding to execute the rest of the T/E Plan.

5. References

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